

BIO-SUSHY

Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

Deliverable D.2.2

One hybrid solvent-based coating with high inorganic content

Deliverable Information

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¹ PU = PUBLIC fully open ((warning) automatically posted online on the Project Results platforms)

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Publishable Summary

The Deliverable D.2.2 "*One hybrid solvent-based coating with high inorganic content*" is presented in this document and aims at presenting the demonstrator coating for the glass case study.

The document describes the characteristics of the demonstrators and their properties after application on glass substrate:

- General characteristics of the demonstrator
- Physico-chemical characteristics of the coating material
- Physico-chemical characteristics of the applied coating.
- Toxicity tests
- Conclusions

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
HCA	Hexadecane contact angle
PFAS	per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
SSbD	Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design
WCA	Water contact angle
WP	Work package

1. Objectives

This deliverable covers the production of a PFAs-free hybrid solvent-based coating with high inorganic content for water and oil repellent properties. In this task, selection and synthesis of additives to promote adhesion and to improve chemical top surface chemistry is based on the substitution of PFAs which has a very low surface tension by a functional group which is accepted and has the lowest surface energy (higher than PFAs). The surface density of this functional group can be increased to make the surface comparable to a monolayer of fluorinated compounds. SIKEMIA dealt with the synthesis of biobased additives to reach performances. Materia Nova is in charge of the formulations of hybrid systems in solvent based solution which could also have the water and oil repelling properties.

Table 1. BIO-SUSHY hybrid solvent-based coating with high inorganic content

BIO-SUSHY Coating materials	% biobased	Ratio inorganic/organic	Solvent	Application process
Hybrid sol gel coating	Up to 25 % (modified fatty acids - biobased linkers)	organic 5-15%	Mix alcohol/water	Spray; Curing : thermal (low temperature)

2. Description

2.1. General characteristics of the demonstrator

The demonstrator is defined by a hybrid solvent-based coatings with high inorganic content. Two types of coating solutions are considered:

- One polydimethylsiloxane-based PFAS free hybrid formulation (GlideSilCoat)
- One cellulose-based PFAS free hybrid formulation (GlideBioCoat).

The demonstrator takes the form of 2 formulations in liquid form. The solutions are stored in a plastic container and consist of different components that are prepared beforehand. The volume of the synthesized solution is about 220 ml with a weight of 200 g in a plastic bottle storage of 250 ml. After the synthesis of the formulation, the product is stable for at least 1 month in ambient conditions (pot life can be extended by storing the product at 4°C).

2.2. Physico-chemical characteristics of the coating material

The hybrid solvent based formulation used to coat material such as glass in our case study relies on the chemical and mechanical properties of the coating but also the toxicology and environmental

impact of the different compounds used to synthesise the product. Thus we proceed as schematized in figure 1.

Figure 1. Scheme of basic sol formulation

The first step is the development of a basic formulation with interesting mechanical (adhesion, cohesion, scratch resistance...) and chemical properties (water contact angle and hexadecane contact angle) with respect to the toxicity data given by WP4 activity.

The basic formulation is named GlideBaseCoat BIO-SUSHY product and the main component is listed in Table 1 below.

IDENTIFICATION	DENOMINATION	CONCENTRATION	HAZARD CLASSIFICATION
CAS : 107-98-2	1-methoxy-2-propanol	< 50-95	H226
CE : 203-539-1			H336
INDEX : 603-064-00-3			
REACH : 01-2119457435-35			
CAS: 64-17-5	Ethanol	< 0,1 – 5	H225
CE : 200-578-6			H319
INDEX : 603-002-00-5			

REACH : 01-2119457610-43-XXXX

CAS : 78-10-4	Tetraethyl orthosilicate	< 0,1-20	H226
CE : 201-083-8			H319
INDEX : 014-005-00-00			H332
REACH : 01-2119496195-28-XXXX			H335

CAS : 2031-67-6	Méthyltriéthoxysilane	< 0,1-5	H226
CE : 217-983-9			
INDEX : -			
REACH : No registration number			

Table 2. Composition of the basic sol formulation GlideBaseCoat

In this basic formulation, additives are incorporated to enhance chemical properties and more specifically the hydrophobic and oleophobic properties.

To substitute PFAs with their intrinsic chemical properties, we have selected compounds based on the surface tension of the functional group. As shown in the figure 2 below, methyl group (-CH₃) has the lowest surface tension, after the fluorinated group.

Figure 2. Surface tension of functional groups

A selection of compounds bearing the methyl group will be incorporated into the sol formulation and the formulation will bring the methyl group at the top surface.

GlideSilCoat BIO-SUSHY product contains polydimethylsiloxane additives to improve water and oil repellency. The GlideBioCoat BIO-SUSHY product contains modified cellulose (Sikemia) to enhance hydrophobicity and oleophobicity, eliminating the need for polydimethylsiloxane and PFAS. This product thus contains biobased materials.

Figure 3. Pictures of the two demonstrators

The general properties of the GlideCoat family are listed in Table 2.

Demonstrators	GlideSilCoat	GlideBioCoat
Odor	Ethanolic	Ethanolic
Colour	Colorless	Colorless
Viscosity (mPa.s)	10	10
Dry content (wt%)	9.6	9.9
pH	4	4

Table 3. General properties of GlideCoat family (viscosity measured with a Brookfield viscometer with a spindle at 200 rpm)

2.3. Physico-chemical characteristics of the applied coating

The formulations were deposited on glass coupons (microscopy slides measuring 2.5 x 7.5 cm²). Before coating the inside of a glass container, this preliminary stage enables the quantification of several mechanical (adhesion, scratch, and thickness) and chemical (water and hexadecane contact angles, sliding angles) characteristics.

Figure 4. Gel film formation after the spray deposition and curing

The formulation was deposited by spray coating (pressure applied 1-3 bars, with 2-10 sprayed layers) followed by a step of curing (100-180°C for 1 hour) in the oven.

The crosslinked coatings were characterized by various techniques to evaluate their physico-chemical properties. The properties of coatings based on GlideSilCoat and GlideBioCoat formulations are shown in Table 3 and Table 4.

For the GlideSilCoat formulation, the durability of this coating was tested in immersion after 14 days in water and in glycerol as illustrated in Figure 5.

Sol formulation	WCA (°)	HCA (°)	Surface energy (Nm/m)	Sliding angle (50µl) (°)	Adhesion	Sclerometer
GlideSilCoat	103 ± 1	36 ± 1	22 ± 1	14 ± 1	Cat 0	30N ok

Table 4. GlideSilCoat physico-chemical properties

GlideSilCoat BIO-SUSHY	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Hydrophobic (WCA 103 ± 2°) <input type="checkbox"/> Oleophobic (HCA 37 ± 1°) <input type="checkbox"/> Low surface energy (22 ± 1 Nm/m) <input type="checkbox"/> Water sliding angle (13 ± 1° for 50µl water) <input type="checkbox"/> Good mechanical properties (Adhesion cat 0 and sclerometer 30N) <input type="checkbox"/> Durability : Immersion test in water (after 14d) : <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: left;"> WCA 103 ± 2° Water sliding angle 21 ± 3° for 50µl water </div> <div style="text-align: left;"> in glycerol (after 14d) WCA 102 ± 1° Water sliding angle 9 ± 2° for 50µl water </div> </div> 	

Figure 5. Evolution of the chemical properties of GlideSilCoat coating after immersion in glycerol and water

Sol formulation	WCA (°)	HCA (°)	Sliding angle (50µl) (°)	Adhesion	Sclerometer
GlideBioCoat	96 ± 1	35 ± 1	12 ± 1	Cat 0	30N ok

Table 5. GlideBioCoat physico-chemical properties

The application of these formulations allows for a coating with an average thickness of approximately 2 µm.

The application by spray coating allows it to form a transparent film, as shown in Figure 4.

A spray gun with a pressurized fluid inlet and a 100 mm Ø1.0 mm extension, featuring a VD3 **rotating nozzle** fed by a 1 L stainless steel pressurized tank, has been used to coat the inner glass container as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Spray deposition with rotating nozzle to cover jam jar and cosmetic jar.

3. Toxicity tests

The GlideBaseCoat product was deposited on a microscope slide to form a film after thermal curing. The samples were sent to ITENE for cell viability studies using the MTT assay to measure metabolic activity.

Figure 6. Cell viability by MTT assay

The results show the viability of the cell after the test.

Figure 7. Results of cell viability by MTT assay with GlideBaseCoat formulation

Moreover, to experimentally assess the risk of BIO-SUSHY coating materials, a bio-membrane sensor coupled with a mini-release accelerator within an online configuration was used to quantify the potential release of the coating.

Figure 8. Electrical and fluidic connections of the biomembrane sensor platform.

The study will inform about the potential release of unsafe products and biomembrane damage.

Figure 9. Activities of the biomembrane in the presence of the GlideCoat family.

The results show that, compared to the control test, no evidence of release from the GlideCoat family coatings based on hybrid content.

4. Conclusions

A biobased and polydimethylsiloxane-based hybrid coating has been developed to replace PFAS compounds achieving both water and oil repellency, known as GlideSilCoat and GlideBioCoat. The samples coated with those formulations show hydrophobic properties (WCA higher than 90°) and oleophobic properties (HCA higher than 35°).

SSbD approach allowed us to replace compounds flagged red in the formulation, which could potentially be replaced by alternatives that could have the same performance with low toxicity (Step 1 and Step 2 of SSbD)

The physico-chemical properties of the formulations are demonstrated on a microscope slide. The product should be applied in the inner glass container. To do so, the formulations were also performed in the inner glass and already show interesting properties as hydrophobic properties but also with regard to the sliding property of the coating.

Regarding to this glass case study, based on CEN/TC411 – Biobased products standard, the calculation of biobased carbon content in dry film is estimated at a value between 5-15% in our biobased formulation (GlideBioCoat). This formulation allowed to reach promising hydrophobicity and oleophobicity properties without the use of PFAS. And the perspective is the improvement of this value up to 25%.